

Self-healing Properties of Carbon-black Impregnated Thermoplastic Polyurethane Processed via Fused Deposition Modelling

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Overview

Since the 1980s that first self-healing materials were developed, different types of self-healing materials and healing mechanisms have been studied in order to develop polymers that are able to heal after damage such as a fracture, fatigue and corrosion so that safer and more durable products can be made. However, most of the researches in this area were focused on self-healing methods of thermosetting materials and few research works have been conducted on thermoplastic-based materials, in comparison. Besides, only few studies have been conducted on three dimensional (3D) printing of self-healing materials.

Thanks to the massive growth of 3D printing as a novel processing technique, this study will focus on the creation of a new structure that promotes self-healing properties of a material system consisting of thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) and the carbon black (CB) as the seeding agent. The schematic of the method used in this study can be seen in the following picture:

Material preparation

- Material preparation started by pulverization of TPU pellets. Afterwards, the prepared TPU powder, dry mixed with Carbon-Black (5 wt%). Then, the prepared mixture was extruded into a filament with the diameter of 2.8 to be used for 3D printing using "Ultimaker 3" 3D-printer.

Sample Preparation

- Once the 3D-printable filament was prepared. Different sets of samples were 3D-printed in dog bone shape for testing tensile properties of the material based on ASTM D412, standard test.

Preparation of G-Code file for 3D-printing

3D-Printing using pure TPU

3D-Printing using TPU-CB

Creating damage in some of the samples

Cutting depth = 0.8mm

Top view

Side view

Experiments and Results

- Tensile test (ASTM D412) applied on different series of 3D printed samples including:
 - A. 3D-Printed **TPU** material- **Not damaged**
 - B. 3D-Printed **TPU-CB** material- **Not damaged**
 - C. 3D-Printed **TPU-CB** material- **Damaged**
 - D. 3D-Printed **TPU-CB** material- **Damaged** and then **Healed**
- Healing efficiency was measured based on the tensile strength of the healed and virgin samples.

$$\eta = \frac{\text{Tensile Strength}_{\text{Healed}} - \text{Tensile Strength}_{\text{Damaged}}}{\text{Tensile Strength}_{\text{Virgin}} - \text{Tensile Strength}_{\text{Damaged}}}$$

- It was demonstrated that the prepared material system has self-healing ability. Healing efficiency was calculated to be 32%.
- Presence of **CB** particles in **TPU** enables absorbing microwave.
- Mechanical properties of TPU enhanced by adding CB.
- Samples were able to heal in less than 20s while the microwave was aimed to the damaged area.

